

A quantitative research of learning habits of secondary school students: An observational study in Dhaka Division

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Abstract

Purpose: This study aimed to identify the significant factors influencing the learning habits of secondary-level students.

Research methodology: This study examined the learning habits of 120 students from 12 high schools in three categories throughout three surrounding cities in the Dhaka Division. This study used a descriptive survey research design. A Purposive sampling approach was applied to select three districts from the Dhaka division, and 12 secondary schools were selected from the three districts. These 120 respondents were chosen using a simple random sampling method belonging to classes 6–10 and ages 12–16.

Results: The average age was 14.0 ± 2.3 years. The majority of the students (39.2%, $n = 47$) came from families with limited income, and most of their mothers were not working (77.5%, $n = 93$). Furthermore, most students (39.2%, $n = 47$) were from poor-class families. Among the three factors influencing learning habits, two (gender and residence status) were statistically significant, but working mothers were statistically insignificant.

Limitations: The results of this study may not accurately reflect the entire situation because data from only 120 students from three districts in the Dhaka division were collected.

Contribution: There is no statistical relationship between study habits and students' mothers' job status. However, gender and residence had an important influence on students' learning habits.

Novelty: The researcher suggests that educators and school authorities work together to convince students how to build efficient study routines and boost their academic and future achievements.

Keywords: Study Habit, Student, Residence Status, Gender, Mother Jobs Status

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1. Introduction

Simple actions and initiatives taken on a daily basis constitute an individual's habits. A person's quality of life is significantly affected by his habits. People's habits mold their personalities and characteristics, which in turn influences their destiny. The term "habits" refers to patterns of automatic, repeating activities that a human performs without thinking about them. All cultures and communities across the world have placed strong emphasis on developing healthy habits to help people live happy and prosperous lives. Undoubtedly, habits play a major role in determining an individual's life course. The term "education" describes a process or action that changes a person's behavior from instinctual to human. This highlights the fundamental idea that education aims to identify a person's aptitudes and

gradually prepare them for social interaction and success. Among the several elements that lead to a successful life, academic accomplishment is seen as one of the most important. A student's ability to succeed academically has become crucial in today's fiercely competitive environment to secure a successful career. Developing good study habits is essential for reaching the required standards of academic achievement.

A study habit may be defined as setting aside a specific, uninterrupted time each day to commit to the process of learning. Students with these learning habits can work hard. As a result, students demonstrated a certain level of constancy in their approach to overcoming exam anxiety through a deliberate and well-planned study schedule. Study habits are mostly extrinsic elements that facilitate learning, such as a well-designed study schedule that covers topics, regular study sessions, self-evaluation, material reviews, and practicing content explanations.

Study habits are patterns of action that students set up when studying as a means of learning. Study habits also demonstrate how often a student engages in regular study activities, which are characterized by a regular study plan that includes the frequency of study sessions, content reviews, and so on, and takes place in a setting that is conducive to learning. Studying attitude is students' favorable attitude toward the specific study activity as well as their acceptance and support of the overall aims of their high school education.

The word "study" refers to a certain type of learning that enables us to fully utilize the power of our minds. Typically, when we say we are going to study, we mean that we are going to work hard, focus, or try to get better at something like reading or writing. We deliberately put a lot of time, effort, and energy into achieving a learning objective. This study focuses on the commitment to gaining more information and skills.

However, students with learning disabilities may still generally have unproductive and inefficient study habits and techniques. Students will better comprehend why they occasionally become irritated by conventional study techniques if they are aware of their learning patterns or styles. He says that as they help ensure a successful academic future, effective study habits are crucial for academic achievement. Having strong study habits can help you get higher grades, and better grades will help you get into better schools and institutions, and maybe even get a scholarship. This results in successful careers.

A student will work more effectively and feel less stress as a result of developing solid study habits, which will help spell success. He continued by saying that productive study habits contribute to an academic setting that is more productive. It is time efficient to prepare the study schedule in advance as a student and stick to it. Students who practice effective study habits are often less anxious. Procrastinators who show up unprepared on exam days are often worried. When it comes to taking exams, students who plan their lives and adhere to their planned study routines are at ease and confident.

According to Palpani (2012), the development of reading culture is crucial to the world's development as a literate civilization. It molds people's personalities, aids in the development of sound thought processes, and generates new concepts. However, changes in mass media have continued to affect people's desire to read books, periodicals, and journals, among others.

Chadha and Chadha (2015) investigated 200 teenage learners Chadha and Chadha (2015) to determine the influences of gender and TV viewing hours on their study habits. Dr. C.P. Mathur created a questionnaire that was used to gather data. Two hundred teenagers from many Tehri Garhwal (Uttarakhand) schools participated in this study. The findings indicated that women had better study habits than boys and that pupils with lower TV viewing habits had better study habits.

Making studying habits fun and lively. Do not put pressure on yourself with the idea of obtaining good results on exams. To understand the unknown and gain knowledge about the surroundings, one should read. Only then will you become interested in your studies, and you will be able to get lost in the infinite ocean of knowledge.

2. Literature Reviews

Gahir, Sahu, and Sahoo (2022) studied the association between secondary school students' study habits and academic success (Gahir, Sahu, & Sahoo, 2022). The correlation results showed a strong positive relationship between secondary school pupils' study habits and academic success. Sasi and Anju (2020) found a statistically significant relationship between study habits and high school students' academic achievement. High school students' study habits and academic achievement were positively correlated.

According to Singh (2019) analysis of senior secondary school students' study habits, there was no discernible variation in the habits of students from rural and urban backgrounds. There was no discernible difference in the study habits of boys and girls, and students from urban backgrounds tended to have better study habits than those from rural backgrounds.

To discover more about the state of study habits and how they relate to academic success, Jafari, Aghaei, and Khatony (2019) performed a study among medical science students in Kermanshah, Iran. At Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences, 380 students studying medical sciences participated in this cross-sectional study. The samples were randomly allocated. The findings indicated that 81.3% of students had good study habits. The findings showed a strong and direct relationship between good study habits and scholastic success.

Sharma (2017) studied secondary school students' study habits and family environments. The research's primary goals were to ascertain how secondary school students' home environments and study habits differed from those of state-board schools in Maharashtra, as well as to investigate the link between the two. The results showed notable differences between the study habits and home environments of boys 'and girls.' The findings of this study showed a strong correlation between study habits and aspects of the home environment.

Academic accomplishment among senior secondary school pupils in connection to study habits was studied by Upadhyay (2017), and the results showed that there were no appreciable variations between male and female senior secondary school pupils' academic achievement.

Ebele and Olofu (2017) investigated study habits and their effects on the academic performance of secondary school students in biology. Ten of fifty senior secondary school pupils from the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, constituted the study's sample. The primary goal of this study was to determine the association between study habits and the academic performance of secondary school students in biology by observing how these habits affect students' academic performance. The conclusions of the research indicated that students in the chosen study region had poor study habits, and they also discovered a strong correlation between their study habits and academic achievement in secondary school.

Alavi, Lesani, and Mahdavinia (2017) examined the study habits and academic performance of two student groups in medical and paramedical fields. The study's conclusions demonstrated a substantial difference between the study habits of paramedical and medical students, with the former having superior study habits than the latter. Additionally, the study found a positive and statistically significant correlation between students' study habits and academic achievement.

Z. N. Khan (2016) looked into "the influence of socioeconomic level as well as sex disparities on study habits of class VII students (100) of government institutions in the Amroha area. Studies have shown that study habits are significantly influenced by gender. Study habits were shown to be unaffected by socioeconomic level in a major way. The interaction between socioeconomic level and sex differences was not significant.

In 2016 research by Arora (2016), a representative sample of one hundred ninth-grade students from senior secondary schools in the Punjabi area of Ludhiana, India, was chosen at random. The grades that the teenagers received on their yearly exams were used as a measure of their academic achievement.

The study also showed that there is a significant beneficial relationship between teenagers' academic achievement and their study habits.

R. M. A. Khan, Iqbal, and Tasneem (2015) evaluated "the influence and impact of parents' educational level on students' academic achievement at the secondary level of education. 200 10th graders were chosen to represent the sample. Students from several public and private high schools in Rajanpur, South Punjab, were photographed. Oral interviews, observations, and questionnaires were used in this study. The findings indicate a substantial beneficial association between adolescents' academic success and their parents' education levels. Education and learning processes play a significant role in academic achievement (Mendezabal, 2013). Indeed, it is a crucial factor in evaluating an individual's overall potential and abilities (Nuthana & Yenagi, 2009), which are often assessed based on test results (Mendezabal, 2013). One may argue that students' intellectual achievement on tests is not solely dependent on instructors' work. To get the most out-of-classroom instruction and perform well on tests, students need to supplement it with engaging and productive after-class work. Therefore, to succeed academically, every student must establish productive study habits. Consequently, there have been shifts in educational paradigms that highlight the value of students working independently throughout the study process and developing the skills required for learning (Klizaitė & Arlauskienė, 2015). The shift from the traditional instructional paradigm to a constructivist learning paradigm, where learning allows learners to engage in intense autonomous activities, makes effective self-study habits more pertinent (Taqui, 2019).

In their 2015 study, Jayanthi and Srinivasan (2015) looked at "the impact of family environment on the academic success in mathematics of kids in the 10th standard. A sample of 1007 kids from two districts in Tamil Nadu was used in this study. A favorable association between family environment and children's academic success in mathematics was found.

Julius and Evans (2015) and Sarker and Uchinlayen (2020) examined the relationship between students' academic performance and their study habits. This descriptive correlational study used a survey design. Spicer Higher Secondary School's 9th graders were among the target demographics. The findings showed a favorable connection between study habits and academic success (0.66). It was evident that neither professors nor students seemed to make an attempt to cultivate excellent study habits.

Studies have shown that readily available educational resources are crucial tools for promoting students' learning habits. The availability and appropriate use of instructional resources are critical for supporting student learning (OA Marcus, 2016; Neji, Ukwetang, & Nja, 2014). Learning engagement and habits are undoubtedly affected by academic performance. (OU Marcus, 2016). According to research, these attributes, together with well-stocked labs and libraries, were somewhat effective in improving students' academic performance, including their learning habits.

Siddiqui and Fatima (2014) examined study habits and academic motivation as two independent factors (Siddiqui and Fatima (2014)) to determine their impact on academic performance. A sample of 278 teenagers in Class X in Aligarh schools participated in the study. The findings showed that study habits had become a determining factor for the male sample's entire population, but not for the female sample. In terms of achievement motivation, the variable has an impact on academic performance for the entire population in the female sample, but not in the male sample.

According to Mphale and Mhlauli (2014) and Sarker (2023), factors have contributed to the decline in student academic performance in junior secondary school in Botswana since 2010. One hundred and twenty people were surveyed for data collection. The findings indicated that several issues, from low staff morale to underprepared students for the exams, might affect students' poor academic achievement.

Studies by Gakhar and Bains (2011), Rajakumar and Soundararajan (2012), Chand (2013), and Promila (2014) have shown that multiple types of demographic factors, such as gender, residential background, academic stream, family type (nuclear or joint), school type (government or private), and parental education, affect the study habits of students enrolled in senior secondary schools. The findings

demonstrated no appreciable variations in the general and focused study habits of secondary school students from nuclear and non-nuclear families. In terms of living conditions, workload schedules, and subject planning, secondary school students attending public schools surpass those attending private schools significantly; however, when it comes to studying habits and exam preparation, private school students outperform public school students significantly. Regarding study habits, female students in the arts and sciences perform better than male students (Promila, 2014).

In their 2014 study, Daniel and Felix (2014) examined how peer pressure and school environment affected students' academic outcomes. The study included 21 public secondary schools in the Sabatia District of Vihiga Nation. Participants were selected using straightforward random selection methods. Multi-regression analysis was used to analyze the data. Analyzing the results, it was found that the academic performance of children was significantly affected by school environment and study pressure. In order to find out how students' study habits and attitudes affect their performance on licensing exams, Mendezabal (2013) did research titled "Study Habits and Attitudes: The Road to Academic Success." The participants were graduates of various university programs in the 2009–2010 academic year. According to the research findings, the participants had good study habits, a generally positive attitude regarding the conduct and teaching methods used in the classroom, and did well on the licensing exams. Students with superior study habits and attitudes performed better on the licensing test.

2.1 Rationale of the study

Studying habits is essential for improving students' academic performance. Researchers have shown that academic performance throughout one's school years has a significant impact on success later in life. The enthusiasm, active study, care, and attention given to children during these years are equally crucial for educational survival and positive adaptations in school. The present study sought to determine whether there were any differences in study habits among secondary school students who were learning in Bangla, English, and Madrasha, since effective study habits are crucial in learning circumstances. The foundation of pupils' eventual study habits is laid throughout the secondary level of education. Policymakers can undertake initiatives to improve study habits by offering facilities to people who have been identified as risk groups using the research findings. Information on how studying influences academic success will be provided to the students. They will become aware of typical study practices among their co-educational pupils as a consequence of the survey's findings. The findings of this study could be useful to other academics conducting related research in the future.

2.2 Purpose of the Study

There is a current uproar among both parents and teachers regarding the learning or reading culture practices of students at the secondary level in Bangladesh. In this age of technology, students have become disinterested in studying habits as they are attracted to various technologies. Consequently, they did not obtain good results. In doing so, both teachers and parents become frustrated. Teachers feel frustrated because their effectiveness is largely judged by society, based on students' academic performance. Social and governmental measures are largely responsible for the poor study habits of secondary-school students. Mothers' current employment status, geographic location, and gender influenced the formation of study habits. However, there may be many factors other than these in students' reading habits, and this study will investigate whether these three factors have any effect.

Even when children's families are literate, they may not receive the support they need to learn and read or they may not have access to resources or a comfortable environment for reading at home. All of these factors have a detrimental impact on pupils' learning habits. An investigation of the variables influencing learning habits among Bangladeshi secondary school students is being conducted in an effort to provide solutions and strategies for assisting pupils in forming positive learning habits.

The goal of this research was to investigate the variables that affect secondary school pupils' study habits in the Dhaka division area of Bangladesh. Therefore, this study specifically aimed to:

1. Ascertain whether students' interests impact their learning habits
2. Investigate whether students' learning habits are influenced by their mothers' professions.
3. Look at if a student's place of living affects their study habits

4. Look at any disparities in the study habits of male and female students.

2.3 Objectives of the Study

The primary goal of this research was to ascertain the importance of variables that encourage diligent study habits among Bangladeshi secondary school students. These elements were originally summarized as follows:

1. To examine the present scenario of the study habits among secondary school students.
2. To Study the significant relationship between study habits and gender among secondary-level students.
3. To determine whether there is any significant relationship between the students' mother's job status and study habits.
4. To determine whether there was any statistically significant relationship between residence status and study habits.

2.4 Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were developed for the investigation and are presented in null form:

H_1 = There are no significant differences in study habits and gender in secondary-level schools

H_2 = There were no significant differences in study habits and students' mother's job status in secondary-level schools.

H_3 = There are no significant differences in study habits and residence status in secondary-level schools

3. Research Methodology

The study, "A study on learning habits among secondary-level students," adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study's total population consisted of students enrolled in various high schools connected to the secondary education department in the Dhaka Division. Three districts and 12 schools were chosen using a purposive sampling approach. In-person interviews and structured questionnaires were used to gather the primary data. Using a standardized questionnaire, 120 respondents from schools (Bangla, Madrasha, and English) provided their comments for this study. These 120 respondents were chosen using a simple random sampling method and belonged to classes 6–10 and ages 12–16. In addition, 12 class teachers were interviewed to determine their opinions on different aspects of students' study habits.

Secondary data were obtained from various sources, including books, journals, articles, newspapers, journals, and associated websites. Demographic factors and study habits were the two main components of the questionnaire. Multiple-choice questions on a five-point Likert scale were created for this study, while adhering to statistical principles and methodologies. Respondents were asked to express their ideas and comments concerning the study habits of Bangladeshi secondary school students openly and honestly. The survey data were then examined using means, standard deviations, percentages, frequencies, and t-tests.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Demographic Characteristics in Secondary -Level Students

Sub-Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Mother Jobs Status		
Working	27	22.5%
Not Working	93	77.5%
Place of Residence		
Rural	60	50.0%
Urban	60	50.0%
Respondents Gender		
Male	60	50.0%
Female	60	50.0%
Family Income Status		

Poor Class	47	39.2%
Middle Class	41	34.2%
Higher Class	32	26.7%
Medium of Instruction		
Bangla	40	33.3%
English	40	33.3%
Madrasha	40	33.3%

Source: Survey Data (2023)

In table 01, 50.0% (n = 60) of the 120 students who participated in the study were male and 50.0% (n = 60) were female. The average age was 14.0 ± 2.3 years. The majority of students (39.2%, n = 47) came from families with limited incomes, and only a small percentage of student mothers (22.5%, n = 27) were working. Forty students (33.3 %) completed each of the three media instructions. The participants were equally distributed between urban and rural regions (50.0%, n = 60).

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Secondary-Level School Students Study Habits Status

Study Habits	Range Of Study Habits Score	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	Above 80%	5	4.2
Good	60% to 80%	34	28.3
Satisfactory	40% to 60%	42	35.0
Poor	20% to 40%	37	30.8
Very Poor	Below 20%	2	1.7
TOTAL		120	100.0

Source: Survey Data (2023)

From table 02, It appears that the second-level school students' study habits status in this study were satisfactory (35%, n = 42), poor, and good (32.5%, n = 39).

Table 3. Model Summary of Gender and Secondary-Level School Students Study Habits

Gender	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	Sig. level (2-tailed)
Male	176.25	69.711	118	-2.075	0.04
Female	203.25	72.785			

Source: Survey Data (2023)

The table 03 makes it abundantly evident that there were major differences between male and female students' study habits. Male students scored 176.25 an average, while female students averaged 203.25; their standard deviations were 72.785 and 69.711, respectively. The value of t was found to be -2.075 when the t-test was used to determine the significance of the difference between these two means. This value is significant at the significance level of 0.05, with 118 degrees of freedom.

While female students' mean scores are higher than those of male students, this indicates that female students have better study habits than male students. The hypothesis claims that "there is no significant difference between male and female students in terms of the measure of "study habits" is rejected.

Table 4. Model Summary of Students Mother Jobs Status and Secondary-Level School Students Study Habits

Students Mother Jobs	Mean	S.D	Df	t-value	Sig. level (2-tailed)
Working	169.30	73.111	118	-1.684	0.095

Not Working	195.69	71.292
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Source: Survey Data (2023)

The table 04 makes it abundantly evident that there were major differences between male and female students' study habits. Working mother scored 169.30 on average, while non-working mothers averaged 193.69; their standard deviations were 73.111 and 71.292, respectively. The value of t was found to be -1.684 when the t-test was used to determine the significance of the difference between these two means. This value is not significant at the 0.05 level of significance and has 118 degrees of freedom.

As the average score of non-working mothers is higher than that of working mothers, this indicates that non-working mothers have better study habits than working mothers. The hypothesis claim that there is no significant difference between working mothers and non-working mothers on the measure of "study habits" is therefore accepted.

Table 5. Model Summary of Residence Status and Secondary-Level School Students Study Habits

Residence Status	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	Sig. level (2-tailed)
Rural	172.88	71.843	118	-2.620	0.01
Urban	206.62	69.194			

Source: Survey Data (2023)

The table 05 makes it widely evident that there were major differences between rural and urban students' study habits. Rural students scored an average of 172.88, whereas urban students scored an average of 206.62, with standard deviations of 71.846 and 69.194, respectively. When the t-test was used to determine the significance of the difference between these two means, the value of the coefficient of t was found to be -2.620, which is significant at a significance level of 0.05, and 198 degrees of freedom. The mean scores of urban students were higher than those of rural students. This indicates that urban students had better study habits than rural students. The hypothesis claims that "there is no significant difference between rural and urban students on the measure of "study habits" study habits is rejected.

4.1 Discussions

Students' academic success is significantly influenced by their academic habits. Researchers have shown that academic performance throughout the school years has a significant impact on success in later life. The enthusiasm, active study, care, and attention given to children during these years are crucial for educational survival and positive adaptations in school. The present study attempted to evaluate the study habits of secondary-level students from diverse educational media (Bangla, English, and Madrasha) since effective study habits are a crucial component in learning settings. In addition, this study attempted to determine whether it varied according to gender, mother's job status, and residence status.

The results of the survey confirmed this intention.

H_1	There are no significant differences in study habits and gender in secondary-level schools	Rejected
H_2	There are no significant differences in study habits and students mother jobs status in secondary-level schools	Accepted
H_3	There are no significant differences in study habits and residence status in secondary-level schools	Rejected

5. Conclusion

However, the significance of this study cannot be stated. The findings of this study may prove helpful to peer groups, parents, teachers, writers, publishers, government officials, and education policymakers who may undertake more research on relevant topics. Peer groups, which are powerful socialization

tools and their roles in influencing students' academic achievement, will be developed to counteract the general declining trend in students' academic performance.

This study's findings, when applied, will assist parents in realizing the importance of providing their children with educational and reading resources. To promote reading and learning, parents should ensure that their house is equipped with tables, seats, adequate lighting, and a noise-free environment. Teachers would be able to concentrate effectively on the learning habits and strategies of their pupils, thanks to the study's findings. Teachers will re-evaluate reading, teaching, and learning strategies in light of this study, as well as any other elements that can compromise sound study habits. Subsequently, they will be able to guide pupils toward the development of efficient learning techniques. By setting up reading competitions and reading clubs, leaders may motivate children to learn and foster the development of positive study habits.

The findings of this study will be beneficial for students and other young people. Keeping this in mind, this outcome will encourage young people and pupils to begin expressing interest in reading. Knowing that it will be difficult to stray from excellent study habits once they have formed them, they will endeavor to do so.

The findings of this study will be advantageous to the authors and publishers. This outcome will enable people to see the necessity of creating biology-related learning and reading resources for classrooms, households, and libraries at reasonable costs. High school students will benefit from this, as they build healthy study habits.

The findings of this study may help the government and educational planners by providing a framework for methodically supplying schools with the infrastructure and learning resources needed to meet the demands of both instructors and students. Through their work, education policymakers may see the need to implement laws that will improve the classroom climate. This will help children to develop productive learning habits.

Finally, it is anticipated that the results of this study will provide an invaluable and practical reference for future scholars working in these and similar fields.

5.1 Limitation

The main limitation of this study is the sample size. It is possible that the answers provided by the participants did not accurately represent current conditions. It was difficult to determine the respondents' emotional states with sufficient accuracy. With this small sample size, the analysis provided about the study habits of students studying at the secondary level in Bangladesh may not be representative of the students of the entire country. The lack of time prevented this study from extending its reach beyond a single divisional region. Financial constraints and the expense of acquiring study materials for transportation have also limited research.

5.2 Recommendations

The biggest obstacle to developing study habits among students is excessive addiction to social media. To free students from this situation, they should be encouraged to engage in co-curriculum activities (such as sports, debate, cultural activities, and scouting). The following points are important for developing good study habits.

1. A beautiful and tidy study room is important for future research.
2. One should develop the habit of studying and persevering regularly and simultaneously. Any gap can divert attention.
3. Eight hours of sleep at night is necessary for students. A good night's sleep will sharpen students' brains and their memories. This will increase their interest in studies
4. Difficult and big problems can be solved very easily if friends conduct regular group studies. Asking each other questions, sharing a small discussion with each other, or presenting the entire topic in front of everyone is possible only through lesson practice.

5. Addiction to electronic devices makes today's students reluctant to read books. To solve this problem, book-reading competition should be organized among the students; as a result, addiction to electronic devices will be prevented and interest in studies will increase.
6. Schools should take steps to implement a Learning Community Plan (LCP) to improve the quality of education (Peregrino, Javillonar, Caballes, Necio, & Ramirez, 2022).

In addition, libraries are the best places to practice studying habits. Earlier, there was an opportunity to read books in neighborhood libraries. Today, this privilege has shrunk significantly. To increase students' habits, library infrastructure should be created at the district and upazila levels. Governments and various NGOs can play an important role in this regard. Reading clubs should be formed at the school level. These clubs and schools occasionally organize reading competitions.

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